

COVARIANCE OF CUBIC SETS

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Abstract:

For given cubic set $\mathcal{A}$, the set $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ of all cubic sets $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) = \{\mathcal{A}^* | \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^* = \mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A}\}$ is the covariance of cubic set of $\mathcal{A}$. The relation between the covariance cubic sets of union, intersection and complement are discussed.

Index Terms: Cubic Set, Internal Cubic Set & External Cubic Set.

Introduction:

In 1965, Zadeh [5] made an extension of the concept of a fuzzy set by an interval-valued fuzzy set. In traditional fuzzy logic, the experts degree of certainty in different statements were given by numbers from the interval [0,1]. It is often difficult for an expert to exactly quantify his or her certainty. Therefore, instead of a real number, it is more adequate to represent this degree of certainty by an interval or even by a fuzzy set. Interval-valued fuzzy sets have been actively used in real-life applications. Cubic sets were discussed by Jun.et.al [3]. Some characterizations on operations on soft sets, Cubic ideals of γ -semigroups were by Chinnadurai.et.al [1, 2].

In this paper, using a fuzzy set, interval-valued fuzzy set and * cubic set, we introduce a new notion called a (interval, external) covariance cubic set and investigate several related properties.

Definition: 1.1 Let X be a nonempty set. A fuzzy set $\mathcal{A}$ in X is characteristic by its membership function (generalized characteristic function).

$$\mu_A : X \rightarrow [0,1]$$

and $\mu_A(x)$ is interpreted as its degree of membership elements x in a fuzzy set A for each $x \in X$. i.e. [0,1] is the subset of nonnegative real numbers whose supremum is finite.

Definition: 1.2 Let X be any set. A mapping $\bar{A} : X \rightarrow D[0,1]$ is called an interval- valued fuzzy subset (briefly, i-v fuzzy subset) of X, where $D[0,1]$ denotes the family of all closed subintervals of [0, 1] and $\bar{A}(x) = [A^-(x), A^+(x)]$ for all $x \in X$, where A^- and A^+ are fuzzy subsets of X such that $A^-(x) \leq A^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

Definition: 1.3 Let X be a nonempty set. A cubic set $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ is a structure of the form $\mathcal{A} = \{ \langle x, A(x), \lambda(x) \rangle | x \in X \}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{ \langle x, B(x), \mu(x) \rangle | x \in X \}$

Then by define * property

$$\mathcal{A}^* = \{ \langle x, A(x), \mu(x) \rangle | x \in X \} \text{ and } \mathcal{B}^* = \{ \langle x, B(x), \lambda(x) \rangle | x \in X \}$$

in which A and B is an interval valued fuzzy set (IVF) in X and λ and μ is a fuzzy set in X.

A cubic set $\mathcal{A}^* = \{ \langle x, A(x), \mu(x) \rangle | x \in X \}$ is simply denoted by $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{ \langle x, B(x), \lambda(x) \rangle | x \in X \}$ is simply denoted by $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$.

Definition: 1.4 Let X be a nonempty set. A cubic set $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ in X said to be internal cubic set (briefly, ICS) if $A^-(x) \leq \mu(x) \leq A^+(x)$ and $B^-(x) \leq \lambda(x) \leq B^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

Definition: 1.5 Let X be a nonempty set. A cubic set $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ in X said to be external cubic set (briefly, ECS) if $\mu(x) \notin (A^-(x), A^+(x))$ and $\lambda(x) \notin (B^-(x), B^+(x))$ for all $x \in X$.

Definition: 1.6 For a family $\{A_i | i \in \wedge\}$ of IVF sets in X where $\wedge$ is an index set, the union $G = \bigcup_{i \in \wedge} A_i$ and

the intersection $F = \bigcap_{i \in \wedge} A_i$ are defined as follows:

$$G(x) = \left(\bigcup_{i \in \wedge} A_i \right)(x) = r \sup_{i \in \wedge} A_i(x) \text{ and,}$$

$$F(x) = \left(\bigcap_{i \in \wedge} A_i \right)(x) = r \inf_{i \in \wedge} A_i(x) \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

Definition: 1.7 Let X be a nonempty set. Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B} = \langle B, \mu \rangle$ be two cubic sets of X. Then $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ be also cubic sets. The class of all cubic sets commutes with $\mathcal{A}^*$,

$$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) = \{ \mathcal{A}^* | \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^* = \mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A} \}$$

is called covariance cubic set.

Example: 1.8 Let X be a nonempty set. A cubic set $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ is defined as

Case 1; $\lambda < \mu$

$\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.4\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.5\}$ then $\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.4\}$. Hence,
 $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\}$
 $\mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\}$

Hence, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) = \{\mathcal{A}^* \mid \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^* = \mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A}\}$.

Case 2; $\lambda > \mu$

$\mathcal{A} = \{[0.6, 0.8], 0.7\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.4, 0.5], 0.5\}$ then $\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.6, 0.8], 0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.4, 0.5], 0.7\}$. Hence,
 $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.6, 0.8], 0.7\}$
 $\mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A} = \{[0.6, 0.8], 0.7\}$

Hence, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) = \{\mathcal{A}^* \mid \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^* = \mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A}\}$.

Definition: 1.9 Let X be a nonempty set. Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B} = \langle B, \mu \rangle$ be two cubic sets of X. Then

$\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ be also cubic sets. The class of all cubic sets commutes with $\mathcal{A}^*$,

$$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{ \mathcal{A}^* \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^*)^c = (\mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A})^c \}$$

is called complement of covariance cubic set.

Example: 1.10 Let X be a nonempty set. A cubic set $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ is defined as $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.4\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.5\}$ then * property as $\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.4\}$. Then,

$$\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\}, (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^*)^c = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.5\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\}, (\mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A})^c = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.5\}$$

Hence, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{ \mathcal{A}^* \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}^*)^c = (\mathcal{A}^*\mathcal{A})^c \}$.

Remark: 1.11 $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \neq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}^c)$ for any $\mathcal{A}$. For example, Let X be a nonempty set. A cubic set $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ is defined as $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.4\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.5\}$ then * property as $\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.4\}$. Then,

$$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\},$$

$$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.5\}.$$

Hence, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \neq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$.

Definition: 1.12 Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B} = \langle B, \mu \rangle$ be cubic sets. Then $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ is defined to be a cubic sets $\mathcal{A}^{*c} = \{ \langle x, A^c(x), 1 - \mu(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$ and $\mathcal{B}^{*c} = \{ \langle x, B^c(x), 1 - \lambda(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$ where $A^c(x) = [1 - A^+(x), 1 - A^-(x)]$ and $B^c(x) = [1 - B^+(x), 1 - B^-(x)]$.

Result: 1.13 For any $\mathcal{A}$, $(\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}))^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}^c)$.

Theorem: 1.14 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be two cubic sets in X. Then $\mathcal{A}^*$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be also two cubic sets in X. If its satisfying the following conditions:

- (1) $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ iff $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.
- (2) $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ iff $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.
- (3) $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ iff $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.
- (4) $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ iff $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Proof:

(1) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$. Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Conversely, let $(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Since, $(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$, $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Thus $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ is always true.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

(2) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$. Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Conversely, let $(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Since, $(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$, $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Thus $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ is always true.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

(3) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$. Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Conversely, let $(\mathcal{A}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Since, $(\mathcal{A}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$, $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Thus $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ is always true.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

(4) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$. Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Conversely, let $(\mathcal{A}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Since, $(\mathcal{A}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$, $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Thus $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ is always true.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$.

Hence proved.

Theorem: 1.15 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be two cubic sets in X . Then $\mathcal{A}^*$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be also two cubic sets in X . If its satisfying the following conditions:

(1) $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$ iff $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

(2) $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$ iff $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

(3) $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$ iff $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

(4) $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$ iff $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Proof: (1) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$. Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Since, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$, $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Thus $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$.

$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$ is always true.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = (\mathcal{A})^c$.

(2) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$. Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Since, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$, $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Thus $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$ is always true.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = (\mathcal{B})^c$.

(3) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$. Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Since, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$, $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Thus $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = (\mathcal{B})^c$.

(4) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$. Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Conversely, let $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Since, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \supseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$, $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$.

Thus $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c$.

$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c$ is always true.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})^c = (\mathcal{A})^c$.

Hence proved.

Remark: 1.16 Union of covariance cubic set is a cubic set. Intersection of covariance cubic set is a cubic set.

Example: 1.17 Let X be a nonempty set. A cubic set $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ is defined as $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.4\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.9\}$ then $\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.9\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.4\}$. Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.9\}$ and $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.1\}$. Therefore, $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.9\}$ and $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.1\}$.

Theorem: 1.18 Demorgan's Law

For any three covariance of cubic sets $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}), \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ and $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})$ we have

$$(1) \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})) = (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})).$$

$$(2) \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})) = (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})).$$

Proof: (1) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $(x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ and $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow (x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}))$ and $(x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}))$ and $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})) \subseteq (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Now let $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Then $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}))$ and $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow (x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}))$ and $(x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $(x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ and $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Hence $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})) = (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

(2) Let $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Then $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ or $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ and $(x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ or $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow (x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ and $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}))$ or $(x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ and $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}))$ or $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})) \subseteq (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Now let $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Then $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}))$ and $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow (x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ and $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}))$ or $(x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ and $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ and $(x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})$ or $x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$ and $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

$\Rightarrow x \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Hence $x \in (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})) \subseteq \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Therefore $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B}) \cup \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C})) = (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{B})) \cup (\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) \cap \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{C}))$.

Hence proved.

Definition: 1.19 Given cubic set $\mathcal{A}$, this exists cubic set $\mathcal{B}$ such that $(\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^c)^c \neq \mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^c$, then $\mathcal{A}$ is called met covariance under $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A})$. i.e,

$$\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{A}) = \{ \mathcal{B} \mid (\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^c)^c \neq \mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^c \}$$

Example: 1.20 Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.4\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.5\}$ be a cubic sets. Let $\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.3, 0.5], 0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.4\}$ be also a cubic sets. Then $\mathcal{A}^c = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.6\}$, $\mathcal{B}^c = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.5\}$, $\mathcal{A}^{*c} = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^{*c} = \{[0.4, 0.6], 0.6\}$ be a cubic sets. Therefore,

$$(\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^c)^c \neq \mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^c$$

Example: 1.21 Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.2, 0.5], 0.9\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.3, 0.7], 0.8\}$ be a cubic sets. Let $\mathcal{A}^* = \{[0.2, 0.5], 0.8\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.3, 0.7], 0.9\}$ be also a cubic sets. Then $\mathcal{A}^c = \{[0.5, 0.8], 0.1\}$, $\mathcal{B}^c = \{[0.3, 0.7], 0.2\}$, $\mathcal{A}^{*c} = \{[0.5, 0.7], 0.2\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^{*c} = \{[0.3, 0.7], 0.1\}$ be a cubic sets. Therefore,

$$(\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^c)^c \neq \mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^c$$

Definition: 1.22 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be a cubic sets. Also $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be a cubic sets. Then we define a form of structure ,

$$G(\mathcal{A}) = \{ \mathcal{B} \mid \mathcal{B} \text{ commutes with } \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A} \text{ and } \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A} \}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}$.

Example: 1.23 Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.2,0.5],0.9\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.3,0.7], 0.8\}$ be a cubic sets. Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.2,0.5], 0.8\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.3,0.7],0.9\}$ be also a cubic sets. Then $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.5,0.8],0.1\}$, $\mathcal{B}^c = \{[0.3,0.7],0.2\}$, $\mathcal{A}^c = \{[0.5,0.7],0.2\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^{*c} = \{[0.3,0.7],0.1\}$ be a cubic sets. Therefore,

$$\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \{[0.2,0.5],0.8\} = \{[0.2,0.5],0.8\},$$

$$\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \{[0.2,0.5],0.8\} = \{[0.2,0.5],0.8\}$$

Example: 1.24 Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3,0.5],0.4\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.4,0.6], 0.5\}$ be a cubic sets. Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3,0.5], 0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.4,0.6],0.4\}$ be also a cubic sets. Then $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.5,0.7],0.6\}$, $\mathcal{B}^c = \{[0.4,0.6],0.5\}$, $\mathcal{A}^c = \{[0.5,0.7],0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^{*c} = \{[0.4,0.6],0.6\}$ be a cubic sets. Therefore,

$$\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \{[0.3,0.5],0.4\} = \{[0.3,0.5],0.4\},$$

$$\mathcal{B}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \{[0.3,0.5],0.5\} = \{[0.3,0.5],0.4\}$$

Definition: 1.25 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be a cubic sets. Also $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be a cubic sets. Then we define a form of structure,

$$G(\mathcal{A}) = \{ \mathcal{B} \mid \mathcal{B} \text{ commutes with } (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c \text{ and } (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c \}.$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c = (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c\mathcal{B}$ and $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c = (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c\mathcal{B}$.

Example: 1.26 Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.2,0.5],0.9\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.3,0.7], 0.8\}$ be a cubic sets. Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.2,0.5], 0.8\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.3,0.7],0.9\}$ be also a cubic sets. Then $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.5,0.8],0.1\}$, $\mathcal{B}^c = \{[0.3,0.7],0.2\}$, $\mathcal{A}^c = \{[0.5,0.7],0.2\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^{*c} = \{[0.3,0.7],0.1\}$ be a cubic sets. Therefore,

$$\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c = (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \{[0.7,0.8],0.8\} = \{[0.7,0.8],0.8\},$$

$$\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c = (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \{[0.7,0.8],0.8\} = \{[0.7,0.8],0.8\}$$

Example: 1.27 Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3,0.5],0.4\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{[0.4,0.6], 0.5\}$ be a cubic sets. Let $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.3,0.5], 0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^* = \{[0.4,0.6],0.4\}$ be also a cubic sets. Then $\mathcal{A} = \{[0.5,0.7],0.6\}$, $\mathcal{B}^c = \{[0.4,0.6],0.5\}$, $\mathcal{A}^c = \{[0.5,0.7],0.5\}$ and $\mathcal{B}^{*c} = \{[0.4,0.6],0.6\}$ be a cubic sets. Therefore,

$$\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c = (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \{[0.5,0.7],0.5\} = \{[0.5,0.7],0.5\},$$

$$\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c = (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c\mathcal{B} \Rightarrow \{[0.5,0.7],0.5\} = \{[0.5,0.7],0.5\}$$

Definition: 1.28 Let X be a nonempty set. Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be a cubic sets of X. Also $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be a cubic sets of X. Then we define a form of structure,

$$(1) \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A}) = \{ x \mid \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}(x) = \mathcal{A}(x), x \in X \} \text{ if } \lambda < \mu.$$

$$(2) \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A}) = \{ x \mid \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}(x) = \mathcal{A}(x), x \in X \} \text{ if } \lambda > \mu.$$

Remark: 1.29 $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})$ when $\lambda = \mu$.

Example: 1.30 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be a cubic sets in X. Also $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be a cubic sets in X. If $\mathcal{A}(x) = [0.3,0.5]$, $\lambda(x) = 0.4$, $\mathcal{B}(x) = [0.4,0.6]$ and $\mu(x) = 0.5$. Then $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A}) = \{ x \mid \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}(x) = \mathcal{A}(x), x \in X \}$ if $\lambda < \mu$.

Example: 1.31 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be a cubic sets in X. Also $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be a cubic sets in X. If $\mathcal{A}(x) = [0.2,0.5]$, $\lambda(x) = 0.9$, $\mathcal{B}(x) = [0.3,0.7]$ and $\mu(x) = 0.8$. Then $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A}) = \{ x \mid \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}(x) = \mathcal{A}(x), x \in X \}$ if $\lambda > \mu$.

Definition: 1.32 Let X be a nonempty set. Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be a cubic sets of X. Also $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be a cubic sets of X. Then we define a form of structure,

$$(1) \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{ x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X \} \text{ if } \lambda < \mu.$$

$$(2) \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{ x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X \} \text{ if } \lambda > \mu.$$

Example: 1.33 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be a cubic sets in X. Also $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be a cubic sets in X. If $\mathcal{A}(x) = [0.3,0.5]$, $\lambda(x) = 0.4$, $\mathcal{B}(x) = [0.4,0.6]$ and $\mu(x) = 0.5$. Then $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{ x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X \}$ if $\lambda < \mu$.

Example: 1.34 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be a cubic sets in X. Also $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}^*$ be a cubic sets in X. If $\mathcal{A}(x) = [0.2,0.5]$, $\lambda(x) = 0.9$, $\mathcal{B}(x) = [0.3,0.7]$ and $\mu(x) = 0.8$. Then $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{ x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X \}$ if $\lambda > \mu$.

Theorem: 1.35 Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \mathcal{A}, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B} = \langle \mathcal{B}, \mu \rangle$ be a cubic set in X. Also let $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mu \rangle$, $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle \mathcal{B}, \lambda \rangle$ be a cubic set in X. If $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})$ is an ICS, then $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c$ is an ICS.

Proof: Since $\mathcal{A} = \langle \mathcal{A}, \lambda \rangle$ is an ICS in X, we have $\mathcal{A}^-(x) \leq \lambda(x) \leq \mathcal{A}^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$. This implies that $1 - \mathcal{A}^+(x) \leq 1 - \lambda(x) \leq 1 - \mathcal{A}^-(x)$. Since $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mu \rangle$ is an ICS in X, we have $\mathcal{A}^-(x) \leq \mu(x) \leq \mathcal{A}^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$. This implies that $1 - \mathcal{A}^+(x) \leq 1 - \mu(x) \leq 1 - \mathcal{A}^-(x)$. By using the definition $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{ x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X \}$. Hence $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c$ is an ICS in X.

Theorem: 1.36 Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \mathcal{A}, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \mathcal{B}, \mu \rangle$ be a cubic set in X. Also let $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mu \rangle$, $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle \mathcal{B}, \lambda \rangle$ be a cubic set in X. If $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})$ is an ECS, then $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c$ is an ECS.

Proof: Since $\mathcal{A} = \langle \mathcal{A}, \lambda \rangle$ is an ECS in X, we have $\lambda(x) \notin (\mathcal{A}^-(x), \mathcal{A}^+(x))$ for all $x \in X$. This implies that $1 - \lambda(x) \notin (1 - \mathcal{A}^+(x), 1 - \mathcal{A}^-(x))$. Since $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle \mathcal{A}, \mu \rangle$ is an ECS in X, we have $\mu(x) \notin (\mathcal{A}^-(x), \mathcal{A}^+(x))$ for all $x \in X$. This implies that $1 - \mu(x) \notin (1 - \mathcal{A}^+(x), 1 - \mathcal{A}^-(x))$. By using the definition $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{ x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X \}$ Hence $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c$ is an ECS.

Theorem: 1.37 Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B} = \langle B, \mu \rangle$ be a cubic set in X . Also let $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$, $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ be a cubic set in X . If $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})$ is an ICS, then $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c$ is an ICS.

Proof: Since $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ is an ICS in X , we have $A^-(x) \leq \lambda(x) \leq A^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$. This implies that $1 - A^+(x) \leq 1 - \lambda(x) \leq 1 - A^-(x)$. Since $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$ is an ICS in X , we have $A^-(x) \leq \mu(x) \leq A^+(x)$ for all $x \in X$. This implies that $1 - A^+(x) \leq 1 - \mu(x) \leq 1 - A^-(x)$. By using the definition $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X\}$. Hence $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c$ is an ICS in X .

Theorem: 1.38 Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{A} = \langle B, \mu \rangle$ be a cubic set in X . Also let $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$, $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ be a cubic set in X . If $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})$ is an ECS, then $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c$ is an ECS.

Proof: Since $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ is an ECS in X , we have $\lambda(x) \notin (A^-(x), A^+(x))$ for all $x \in X$. This implies that $1 - \lambda(x) \notin (1 - A^+(x), 1 - A^-(x))$. Since $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$ is an ECS in X , we have $\mu(x) \notin (A^-(x), A^+(x))$ for all $x \in X$. This implies that $1 - \mu(x) \notin (1 - A^+(x), 1 - A^-(x))$. By using the definition, $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X\}$. Hence $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c$ is an ECS.

Theorem: 1.39 Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B} = \langle B, \mu \rangle$ be a cubic set in X . Also let $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$, $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ be a cubic set in X . Then $(\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c)^c = \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})$.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X\}$.

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c)^c &= \{x \mid ((\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x))^c = (\mathcal{A}^c(x))^c, x \in X\} \\ &= \{x \mid ((1 - A^+(x), 1 - A^-(x))^c)^c = ((1 - A^+(x), 1 - A^-(x))^c)^c, x \in X\} \\ &= \{x \mid (A^-(x), A^+(x)) = (A^-(x), A^+(x)), x \in X\} \\ &= \{x \mid \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}(x) = \mathcal{A}(x), x \in X\} \end{aligned}$$

$$(\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A})^c)^c = \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A}).$$

Theorem: 1.40 Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \lambda \rangle$ and $\mathcal{B} = \langle B, \mu \rangle$ be a cubic set in X . Also let $\mathcal{A}^* = \langle A, \mu \rangle$, $\mathcal{B}^* = \langle B, \lambda \rangle$ be a cubic set in X . Then $(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c)^c = \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})$.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c = \{x \mid (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x) = \mathcal{A}^c(x), x \in X\}$

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c)^c &= \{x \mid ((\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A})^c(x))^c = (\mathcal{A}^c(x))^c, x \in X\} \\ &= \{x \mid ((1 - A^+(x), 1 - A^-(x))^c)^c = ((1 - A^+(x), 1 - A^-(x))^c)^c, x \in X\} \\ &= \{x \mid (A^-(x), A^+(x)) = (A^-(x), A^+(x)), x \in X\} \\ &= \{x \mid \mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{A}(x) = \mathcal{A}(x), x \in X\} \end{aligned}$$

$$(\mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A})^c)^c = \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{A}).$$

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